

THEORISING THE INTEGRATION OF ECONOMIC MIGRANTS IN
THE LIFE OF HOST COUNTRIES (WITH EMPHASIS ON EU
MEMBER STATES)

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ABSTRACT: Migration should be addressed as a natural human endeavour while economic migrants should not be viewed as poor people seeking employment abroad. Economic migration, when carried out according to the relevant rules and regulations has advantages for the migrants themselves, for the countries of origin and for the countries of destination. The latter cannot avoid to deal with the question of the full participation and integration of migrant workers in their socio-economic and political life, a difficult question for many EU Member States but a very significant one given the projected continuous inward migration flows.

KEYWORDS: migration – migrant workers – socio-economic integration – European Union – Blue Card regime

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I. INTRODUCTION

It would be wrong to consider that the question of migratory waves towards host countries is only of concern to the countries of the undeveloped or the developing world. Migration is a process occurring between countries of the so-called First World, where it could take the form of high-skilled individuals migrating between countries sharing comparable economic characteristics,¹ between countries of the so-called Third World but also between countries of the First and the Third World. Indeed, it should be irrelevant the citizens of which state are migrating to which state, because all migrants should, on principle, be treated equally. This submission flows from the general principle of non-discrimination, a fundamental rule of international law which transcends international relations as well. This has been expressly recognized in many international treaties, including the global and regional instruments protecting human rights and fundamental freedoms.² True, as this submission is, there is an important caveat because both the process of emigration and the process of immigration are within the ambit of State sovereignty. Therefore, countries of origin are within their rights to impose restrictions on their citizens leaving their territory while countries of destination may very well prohibit the entry of foreigners (or third country nationals in European Union (EU) parlance).

The present article focuses on legal migration undertaken for economic purposes. It is not concerned with illegal, illicit, clandestine or undocumented migration or with refugees and asylum seekers. After arguing that, on the whole, migration should be addressed as a natural human endeavour and that economic migrants should not be viewed within the confines of such stereotypes as poor people desperately seeking employment abroad, the article seeks to examine the advantages

¹ See U. Kreickemeier and J. Wrona 'Two-Way Migration between Similar Countries' (2016) *The World Economy* Online Version, [http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/10.1111/\(ISSN\)1467-9701/issues](http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/10.1111/(ISSN)1467-9701/issues)

² See, inter alia, Art. 2 of the Universal Declaration on Human Rights (1948), Art. 2 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (1966), Art. 2 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (1981), and Art. 3(1) of the Arab Charter on Human Rights (2004). See further Art. 1(1) of the UN International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of all Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families (1990).

that economic migration has for the migrants themselves, for the countries of origin and for the countries of destination. It also discusses the ever current but thorny issue of the participation and integration of migrant workers in the host countries' economic and political life as well as in their social fabric.

II. DISPELLING SOME COMMON MISUNDERSTANDINGS ABOUT MIGRATION

Since ancient times people have always migrated and they are bound to do so for as long as different conditions prevail in different parts of the world and for as long as man strives to achieve a better quality of life for himself/herself and for family members. Migratory waves within continents and between continents have continuously been a reality and have often shaped domestic politics, regional dealings and international relations. In the process they have led to serious problems but they have also offered unique opportunities. Although people migrate for a number of grounds, it is mostly economic reasons which let them take the decision to move to another country. This usually means taking up paid employment or offering their services abroad. It is only logical and within human nature that people will strive to secure a better paid job elsewhere or employment corresponding more closely to their skills and experience or a job which makes them happier. In the integrated and globalized world of today finding (more) suitable employment elsewhere should be regarded as a natural endeavour consistent with the legitimate attempt to develop one's personality. Even though there exists voluntary migration to escape the 'bad' at home only to be find oneself trapped in a 'bad' at the country of destination,³ it would be wrong to view migration pursued for economic reasons simply in the context of people from poor and destitute states desperately seeking jobs in rich(er) states or people from countries with very high unemployment emigrating because the prospect of having any job elsewhere is probably better than having no job at all at home.

³ E.g. migration resulting in humiliating work abroad, including prostitution, see O. Stark and C.S. Fan, 'Migration for degrading work as an escape from humiliation' (2011) 77 *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization* 241-247.

These realities are best described in the opening lines of the New York Declaration for Refugees and Migrants adopted by the high level meeting at United Nations Headquarters on 19 September 2016 to address the question of large movements of refugees and migrants:

Since earliest times, humanity has been on the move. Some people move in search of new economic opportunities and horizons. Others move to escape armed conflict, poverty, food insecurity, persecution, terrorism, or human rights violations and abuses [...] others in response to the adverse effects of climate change, natural disasters ... or other environmental factors. Many move, indeed, for a combination of these reasons.⁴

Arguably the stereotypes mentioned above have been heavily influenced by the migratory waves which southern European states has recently experienced originating from African and Asian countries having in power dictatorial regimes and/or plagued by internal strife and civil wars. However, these realities could lead to distorted conclusions and assumptions. Thus, it should be emphasized that migration is an endeavour covering all human beings. It is a process solely concerning poor and impoverished people looking for a brighter future elsewhere. On the contrary, it engulfs everyone, irrespective of origin, position, skills, wealth, language, religion, etc., who has taken the decision to seek new employment opportunities elsewhere. For example, a person who moves to work as the chief executive officer of a large company in another country is also an economic migrant. While s/he might not be concerned with those things which are important to an unskilled migrant worker, both should be accorded the same legal status in the host country, namely that of an economic migrant.

The aforementioned principle of non-discrimination denotes that all are entitled to receive the same protection and be offered the same benefits, in short

⁴ UN Doc. A/71/L.1, 13 September 2016, https://refugeesmigrants.un.org/sites/default/files/a_71_11.pdf. The Declaration largely reflects the Outcome Document produced in preparation of the meeting and agreed by consensus on 2 August 2016, <http://www.un.org/pga/70/wp-content/uploads/sites/10/2015/08/HLM-on-addressing-large-movements-of-refugees-and-migrants-Draft-Declaration-5-August-2016.pdf>.

receive the same treatment, unless there are specific but objective reasons and policies justifying different conduct by host countries. For means of illustration, reference will be made to the European Union which in 2009 introduced the regime of Blue Card holders. It concerns highly qualified foreigners enjoying in the territory of Member States a number of rights and benefits which are additional to those given to all immigrants.⁵ The EU's goal is to address the labour shortages in specific economic sectors through fostering the admission and mobility of third country nationals but solely for the purposes of highly qualified employment. By offering the Blue Card status, the EU expects to become more attractive to this category of migrants compared to other popular countries of destinations (principally the USA) and also to sustain its global competitiveness and economic growth. Thus, the EU and its Member States, as host countries, are in competition with third states to attract the better skilled migrant workers, to cover scarcities in their labour markets, and boost a fast ageing population. However, as was noted by the European Commission when evaluating the first years of the regime's operation, the national schemes for attracting very skilled migrants not only compete with the Blue Card regime but also with each other.⁶

It follows that the element of competition among host countries could be a factor of some importance in transnational migration.⁷ From the point of view of migrant workers, competition could influence their selection of country of destination. Indeed, in the course of the migration process where people make choices concerning their own life and, where applicable, the life of their families as well. To live and work or be economically active in State A and not in State B or in State C is an exercise in choosing among different venues, possibilities and options. These are choices for which only the migrant workers should take fully responsibility and,

⁵ See Council Directive 2009/50/EC of 25 May 2009 on the conditions of entry and residence of third-country nationals for the purposes of highly qualified employment, OJ L 155, 18.6.2009, p. 17.

⁶ See Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on the implementation of Directive 2009/50/EC on the conditions of entry and residence of third-country nationals for the purpose of highly qualified employment ("EU Blue Card"), COM(2014) 0287 final of 22 May 2014, p. 14.

⁷ F. Docquier and J. Machado, 'Global Competition for Attracting Talents and the World Economy' (2016) 39 *The World Economy* 530–542.

therefore, they should be in the position to address any and all negative outcomes without having to rely on the country of destination for solutions, assistance and aid. As has been argued, “[i]ndividuals make the migration decision by considering the values of the various alternatives, and choosing the option that best suits them given the financial and legal constraints that regulate the international migration process”.⁸

For present purposes, migration should be viewed as a classless, gender neutral and nationality disinterested process which involves leaving one state (the country of origin) for the specific purpose of moving, living and be engaged in (some sort) of gainful employment in another state (the host country or country of destination) for a certain period of time which could extend until the end of the migrant’s work life or even after that. The ability of people to make choices is closely connected with the notion of the autonomy of human beings. The latter is tantamount to one person being completely independent of any other person as well as to the principle of self-determination, namely the freedom to decide one’s own future as s/he thinks fit. As has been argued, autonomy and freedom of choice a.re critical to well-being, while choice is critical to achieving freedom and autonomy.⁹

III. THE ADVANTAGES OF LEGAL ECONOMIC MIGRATION FOR MIGRANTS, FOR THE COUNTRIES OF ORIGIN AND FOR THE COUNTRIES OF DESTINATION

Economic migration, when carried out by following the relevant regulatory framework and acting within its confines, could have significant results for the countries of destination, the countries of origin and the migrants themselves. This reality was expressly recognized in the Declaration approved by the UN Member States following Summit adopting the post-2015 Development Agenda in September 2015. In particular, they recognized, on the one hand, the positive contribution that migrants have as regards inclusive growth and sustainable development and, on the other hand, that transnational migration is a multidimensional reality of major

⁸ See G.J. Borjas, ‘Economic Theory and International Migration’ [1989] 23 *The International Migration Review* 457-485, 460.

⁹ See B. Schwartz, *Paradox of Choice: Why More is Less*, New York: Harper Perennial, 2004.

relevance for the development of countries of origin, of transit countries and of countries of destination and, therefore, coherent and comprehensive responses are needed.¹⁰

As far as the countries of destination are concerned, migration could alleviate any worker shortages experienced by means of 'importing' worker surpluses from other countries and could also contribute to reversing a diminishing population by adding new births. Regarding countries of origin, they would also benefit because it would relieve their economies of excess workforce which cannot be absorbed and has a heavy toll on state finances and the social security system. Thus the 'exportation' of migrants could lead to curtailing domestic unemployment but also to upgrading employment conditions. While these might be theoretical propositions and the prevailing realities might be very different, the possibility cannot be excluded that such migratory waves culminate in equilibrium between the human resources of State A, of State B and/ or of State C. As a direct result, some or all of these States could experience boosted economies and larger receipts from direct and indirect taxation, from social security contributions, from migrants' remittances, and so on.

The above situation could be illustrated by invoking simple market rules: surplus production (S) in one market is not a good thing, underproduction (U) in another market is also a bad thing. Both negative conditions could be corrected, if part of S is transformed into more U, with the end result being that S is equal to U or nears U and both markets have the same production. This transformation may involve significant resources being shifted and may require other adjustments and corrections to be made. Moreover, they invariably demand significant modifications, changes and possibly personal sacrifices as well. But these should be regarded as acceptable if the end result is to be achieved.

As far as migrant workers are concerned, by taking up paid employment in a foreign state they support themselves and any accompanying family members. But they additionally support the country of origin by sending back their earnings, savings

¹⁰ See para. 29 of the Declaration attached to UNGA Resolution 70/1, Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, 25 September 2015.

and investments. Finally, they contribute directly to the host country's economy by paying income taxes, other indirect taxes and social security contributions and indirectly by spending their earnings and savings. For many states migrants' remittances constitute an important source of income.¹¹ It has been suggested that they encourage financial development in developing countries.¹² As has also been argued that the national economies of certain states (including Albania and Lebanon) would have collapsed had it not been for these remittances.¹³ A country might not have an exports driven economy. But what it lacks in income from manufactured goods, commodities or services could, at least partially, be replaced from such inflows. Or it could be that they improve its foreign currency reserves.¹⁴

The World Bank has compiled data on the amounts received by countries of origin as remittances, which are globally estimated at 581,640 million USD for the year 2015 alone. These data make reveal that some states survive on inflows from migrants. For example in Nepal, Tajikistan, Tonga, Kyrgyzstan, Liberia and Moldova migrants' remittances make up at least 25% of their GDP, while in other states (e.g. Armenia, Bermuda, Comoros, The Gambia, Haiti, Honduras, Lebanon, Lesotho, etc.) they make up between 16% and 23% of their GDP (2014 data).¹⁵ Finally, it should be mentioned that in absolute numbers some states have significant remittances (e.g. India 69 billion USD, China 64 billion USD, France 23 billion USD, Nigeria 20,6

¹¹ Generally, see D. Ratha, "Worker's Remittances: An important and stable source of external Finance" in International Bank for Reconstruction and Development/World Bank, *Global Development Finance: Striving for Stability in Development Finance*, Washington, DC: World Bank, 2003, p. 157.

¹² See R. Aggrawal, A. Demircuc-Kunt, and M.S. Martinez Peria, *Do Remittances Promote Financial Development?*, World Bank Policy Research Working Paper No. 3957, June 2006, http://siteresources.worldbank.org/INTTOPCONF3/Resources/Do_Workers_Remittances_Promote_Financial_Development.pdf.

¹³ See P. Levitt and N. Nyberg-Sørensen, *The transnational turn in migration studies*, Global Migration Perspectives, No. 6, October 2004, Geneva: Global Commission on International Migration, p. 3, https://www.iom.int/jahia/webdav/site/myjahiasite/shared/shared/mainsite/policy_and_research/gcim/gmp/gmp6.pdf.

¹⁴ See M. Le Goff and S. Salomone, 'Remittances and the Changing Composition of Migration' (2016) 39 *The World Economy* 513-529.

¹⁵ See World Bank, *Migration and Remittances Data*, at: <http://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/migrationremittancesdiasporaissues/brief/migration-remittances-data>, visited 3 October 2016.

billion USD (2015 estimates)) but due to the magnitude of their economies, they constitute only a very small percentage of their GDP.¹⁶

IV. ECONOMIC MIGRATION IS MUCH MORE THAN WORKING: MIGRANT WORKERS' PARTICIPATION AND INTEGRATION IN HOST COUNTRIES

For economic migrants, living in host countries entails far more than simply being in paid employment. After all, working takes up only a part of a person's daily life. For the rest of the time, their physical presence in the host country cannot but entail participating in its social fabric. Over the years, this partaking could and should at some stage lead to their integration in the host country. But this is neither a straightforward nor a natural development and could prove a complicated task for the migrants but also for the host country and its citizenry. There are certain factors which directly or indirectly affect and complicate the road towards integration: they usually concern the different language, religion, ethics and customs, education,¹⁷ etc., of the migrants and of the citizens in the host countries respectively.

However, these differences should not lead to the migrant workers becoming a second rate group within the host country's population. Contemporary global human rights norms¹⁸ dictate that anyone, irrespective of nationality, being legally resident in a state ought to be treated with respect and have his fundamental freedoms protected without unjustified state interference in his private life. These norms do not take away a host country's right to give more privileges and benefits to its own nationals, which is based on the legal bond of citizenship. However, this consideration does not negate the obligation to secure to foreigners a minimum measure of protection, assistance and services. Whether these would include free schooling for migrants' children, vocational training for unskilled migrant workers, free hospital treatment, etc., is within the host country's prerogative to decide. But not so for the unhindered access

¹⁶ Ibid.

¹⁷ See European Commission, *Employment and Social Developments in Europe 2015*, 21 January 2016, p. 14, <http://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=738&langId=en&pubId=7859&furtherPubs=yes>

¹⁸ Cf. Art. 34(5) of the Arab Charter on Human Rights: 'Every State Party shall ensure protection to workers migrating to its territory in accordance with its laws'.

to justice or for the freedom to assembly, as these are fundamental freedoms applying to everyone and must be constantly guaranteed and ensured.

The process of integration is initially rather one-direction: migrant workers should adapt to the prevailing conditions in the host country and harmonize their life and behaviour accordingly. But later it becomes a two-direction process because the host country makes available services, facilities and amenities to cater for the needs of its immigrant population. It is clearly to its advantage to provide special school classes taught in the migrants' mother tongues, to arrange for appropriate worship places to practice their religious duties freely, to offer access to tertiary education (possibly by taking into account the education acquired at the country of origin), and so on. This two-direction process is based on a *quid pro quo* arrangement: migrants undertake to comply with the host country's rules and regulations and the latter assists them in a number of different ways, including to retain, if they so wish, their language, religion, morals and other elements of their civilization, which characterizes and differentiates them and gives them pride.

Of course there is there is no guarantee that the integration process leading to the full participation of migrant workers in all aspects of the host country's life will be a successful one. For many a migrant a host country might be regarded as something foreign, distant, remote and inaccessible. Thus, integration could turn out to be a positive process for some migrants but not for others. Notwithstanding this consideration, it is imperative that the outcome should always be balanced and mutually beneficial for the immigrant population but also for the host country and its population. Only if all stakeholders in the integration process stand to gain from it, will they be committed to achieving tangible and intangible goals. One of the intangible goals, which is of particular significance and easily overlooked, is trust. A rapport of trust between the migrants and the host country and vice versa should always exist, especially when the immigrant population is quite different from the indigenous population.¹⁹ Effectively this means, on the one hand, that the host country

¹⁹ See P. Thisted Dinesen and M. Hooghe, 'When in Rome, Do as the Romans Do: The Acculturation of Generalized Trust among Immigrants in Western Europe' (2010) 44 *The International Migration Review* 697-727.

expects migrants to be a reliable component of its population and unfailingly observe its laws, rules and regulations and, on the other hand, that migrants expect the host country to treat them with respect and with equality (the aforementioned principle of non-discrimination) and not to take without good reason measures affecting their personal status (e.g. expulsion). As eloquently put by a Congolese who has been living and working in Austria for many years: “When you arrive [at the host country] it is your own duty to integrate, you have to follow the rules”.²⁰ If both sides keep their part of the bargain and trust is grounded in their relationship, the goal of integration would be achieved to a large extent.

Integration does have different meanings depending on whether it is approached from the viewpoint of migrant workers, the host country or the country of origin. As regards the former, it could vary considerably. For some it could mean being socially accepted by the indigenous population, a fact which could lead to societal interaction (including matrimony). For others it could be the first major step towards naturalization. And for others it could mean that they live in a secure environment and enjoy a better quality of life than before. Naturally what constitutes a ‘better quality of life’ is subjective and has to do with how good or how bad were living conditions before emigration. Moreover, it will be argued that integration does not mean assimilation: migrants are absorbed by host countries and are taken over culturally. Naturally if migrants wish to abandon links with the country of origin and be fully immersed in all aspects of the host country’s life, they are entitled to do so. However, if they choose not to and, especially if they are later naturalized as citizens of the host country, they should be free to retain their cultural and social characteristics.

As regards host countries, integration would no doubt be an affirmation that migrant workers are now part of their population and, while there is a clear separation between them and the population *qua* citizens, this is a predominantly political / legal separation compared to the economic / social division. This is explained by the fact that immigrants are, for example, not granted the right to vote and stand as candidates in parliamentary (general) elections and in municipal (local authority) elections or

²⁰ See ‘Getting the new arrivals to work’, *The Economist*, 12 December 2015, p. 61.

they cannot be appointed or hold public posts,²¹ etc.²² But, at the same time, the output of immigrants is included in the host countries' GDP, their deposits and loans are included in the balance sheets of the banks operating in host countries, the birth of their children is included in the host countries' total number of births (possibly turning a negative birth/death ratio into a positive one), and so on.

Despite the positive input that immigrants have (or should have) in host countries, there is no doubt that their integration comes at a cost and involves a financial burden, which for other countries it will be easier to carry, for others more difficult and for others it might require diverting funding earmarked for the indigenous population. In particular, for those European states with double digit unemployment and a huge public debt to service having to finance migrants' socio-economic integration could pose unsurpassable obstacles for the government of the day which, at the same time, runs the risk of being denounced by the opposition for wasting scarce funds to foreigners. Even though European states have access to European Union's funding mechanisms, these might not be sufficient and their impact might be limited.

The EU has recognized the valuable role that immigration plays in strengthening its competitiveness, in addressing demographic shortages and in filling labour scarcities but has also realized that maximizing these benefits requires the successful integration of migrants. Thus, in 2007 it decided to operate until 2013 a European Fund for the Integration of non-EU immigrants (EIF) with an allocated total budget of 825 million Euro which would primarily target newly arrived immigrants.²³

²¹ Note that in federal/federated states the situation may differ from one state to the other, see O. Schmidtke, 'Beyond National Models? Governing migration and integration at the regional and local levels in Canada and Germany' [2014] 2 *Comparative Migration Studies* 77.

²² The reference here is to first generation of migrant workers; the attitudes of second and subsequent generations may or may not vary, see R. Maxwell, 'Evaluating Migrant Integration: Political Attitudes Across Generations in Europe' (2010) 44 *The International Migration Review* 25-52.

²³ Council Decision of 25 June 2007 establishing the European Fund for the Integration of third-country nationals for the period 2007 to 2013 as part of the General programme 'Solidarity and Management of Migration Flows', O.J. 28.6.2007 L 168/18.

The successor funding mechanism, the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF), was also set up for a seven-year period (2014-2020).²⁴ The very title of the mechanism as well as its mission statement (promoting the efficient management of migration flows as well as developing and implementing a common EU approach to asylum and immigration) reveals how dramatically the situation has changed since 2007 resulting in overhauling priorities and downgrading the process of integration. Thus AMIF has four objectives three of which have to do with asylum and only the fourth aims at supporting legal migration to Member States consistent with requirements in their labour markets and the third country nationals' integration. Even though the AMIF budget was almost quadrupled compared to EIF totaling 3.137 billion Euro, it pales to the asylum-related costs projected only by the German federal government and amounting to 100 billion Euro over the period 2016-2020.²⁵

Finally, as regards the countries of origin, the integration of their nationals in third countries would probably depend on national policies on emigration, which often come within the term 'diaspora strategies'.²⁶ Depending on the country of origin, these policies could e.g. concern how to engage high-skilled migrants in fast-tracking domestic development schemes or, in cases of very large number of migrant workers, how to turn their earnings and savings into remittances and channel them in

²⁴ European Parliament and Council Regulation 516/2014 of 16 April 2014 establishing the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund, amending Council Decision 2008/381/EC and repealing Decisions No 573/2007/EC and No 575/2007/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council, See also European Parliament and Council Regulation 514/2014 of 16 April 2014 laying down general provisions on the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund and on the instrument for financial support for police cooperation, preventing and combating crime, and crisis management, O.J. 20.5.2014 L 150/112.

²⁵ See "Can we do this?" - The costs of the migrant crisis', *Deutsche Welle*, 23 August 2016, <http://www.dw.com>

²⁶ For an overview of such strategies, see D. Ancien, M. Boyle and R. Kitchin, Exploring Diaspora Strategies: An International Comparison, Maynooth University, Workshop report, June 2009, http://eprints.maynoothuniversity.ie/2053/1/RK_Exploring_Diaspora_Strategies_International_Comparison.pdf

financing domestic development schemes.²⁷ But countries of origin could also go as far as theorizing emigrants as an extension of their nation in the country of destination. There is an actual precedent for this kind of thinking. Thus on two occasions, in 1997 and in 2001, the then Presidents of Mexico, respectively Ernesto Zedillo and Vicente Fox, declared that the Mexican nation extends beyond the territory enclosed by its borders as a result of the millions of Mexican nationals living (not always legally) abroad, principally in the USA.²⁸ These were important official statements revealing that Mexico considered that migrant workers take with them its civilization and way of life so that, even if they lived and worked abroad for many years, they still consider themselves Mexicans and the same was true for the Mexican state itself.

As explained, host countries are fully within their rights to decide that integration will not extend to migrants' partaking in the political life, at least as far as electoral processes are concerned (although for aliens to become members of political parties is not generally disputed).²⁹ Of course there are exceptions: in a number of European states it may be possible for third country nationals, i.e. those not having the nationality of one of the 28 EU Member States, to partake in local elections.³⁰ The very progressive position in the EU, which grants to aliens having the nationality of another Member State the right to vote and to stand as candidates at local elections in

²⁷ But see H. de Haas, 'Migration and Development: A Theoretical Perspective' (2010) 44 *The International Migration Review* 227-264 who argues that to celebrate migration as self-help development 'from below' is naïve.

²⁸ Cited in W. Lutton, "The Mexican Conquest of the Southwest", *The Social Contract*, Spring 2002, p. 229, <http://www.thesocialcontract.com/pdf/twelve-three/xii-3-229.pdf> and in L. Pries, *Transnational Migration: New Challenges for Nation States and New Opportunities for Regional and Global Development*, Center for International Relations, Reports & Analyses 1/06, Warsaw, p. 11, http://pdc.ceu.hu/archive/00004803/01/rap_i_an_0106a.pdf

²⁹ Cf. J.C. Triviño, *Immigrant Organizations and the Politicization of Cultural Diversity in the City*, MPC Analytical and Synthetic Note 2014/03, European University Institute, Robert Schuman Centre for Advanced Studies, Migration Policy Centre, Florence, 2014.

³⁰ For an overview, see Migrant Integration Policy Index 2015, <http://www.mipex.eu/political-participation>

the Member State in which they live, is the result of political integration pursued at a supranational level.³¹

Thus, with the exception just mentioned, the process of participation and integration is not about political participation and integration. This is reserved for the citizenry, for those migrants who are accepted as citizens through the process of naturalization and for other categories of aliens, who, for historical or other reasons, are allowed to vote, for example the citizens of the (former British) Commonwealth in general elections in the United Kingdom,³² the citizens of certain South American states in local elections in Spain,³³ the citizens of states participating in the Community of Portuguese Language Countries in local elections in Portugal.³⁴ Arguably political integration may not be one of migrants' top priorities. They may not be that much interested in participating in national elections every four or five years or to vote for the city mayor or the local commune's chairperson.

On the other hand, what might be of more importance to migrants is their active participation in the educational system and in the economic life of the host country. The former will allow them to attend, subject to objective criteria and requirements which must also be fulfilled by nationals, all levels of education and/or have access to vocational training. The latter is much broader than the taking up of paid employment by economic migrants. Depending on the host country's domestic legislation, it focuses on the ability and/or the right of migrants to partake in its economic life in ways which are comparable to those applicable to citizens. Thus, while for the latter it is more than obvious that they will have unhindered access to all

³¹ Cf. Art. 22(1) of the Treaty on European Union: 'Every citizen of the [European] Union residing in a Member State of which he is not a national shall have the right to vote and to stand as a candidate at municipal elections in the Member State in which he resides, under the same conditions as nationals of that State'. The latter stipulation is a manifestation of the principle prohibiting discrimination on the ground of nationality. Art. 22(1) is repeated in Art. 40 of the (legally binding) Charter on Fundamental Rights of the European Union which forms part of EU citizens' rights.

³² See B.H. Weston and A. Grear, *Human Rights in the World Community*, 4th ed., University of Pennsylvania Press, Philadelphia, 2016, p. 157.

³³ These rights are awarded on the basis of bilateral agreements and are subject to reciprocity.

³⁴ See C. Healy, *Access to Electoral Rights – Portugal*, European University Institute, Robert Schuman Centre for Advanced Studies, EUDO Citizenship Observatory, Florence, June 2013.

aspects of the economic life, this is not at all obvious for migrants. Indeed, there might be instances where, on account of the reason justifying their presence in the host country, migrants may not be allowed to be economically active, e.g. when they have immigrated to the host country for the purpose of studying or for the purpose of family reunification.

Migrants' partaking in the economic life of the host country could take a number of different forms. One form could be for migrants to set up their own businesses, in other words to become entrepreneurs in their own right. Even the setting up a 'corner shop' or a grocery shop by migrants, who had originally come to the host country as workers, constitutes a significant form of participation in its economic life: the migrant becomes a businessperson and the host country must treat him/her on equal terms with domestic businesspersons. It follows that the migrant should receive the operating licence on the same conditions as domestic businesspersons, pay the same taxes, borrow money from the banks under the same criteria, etc. A second form, which follows logically from the previous one, is for migrants to become themselves employers and hire other migrant workers but also nationals of the host country.³⁵ Again, as employer the migrant should be treated by the host country on terms equal to those regulating domestic employers. The fact that he/she is of a different nationality is not a legitimate ground to justify different treatment, which, as the case might be, could translate to significantly more obstacles, cumbersome procedures and less freedom of action.

A third form could be for properly qualified migrants to seek and obtain a state license to pursue one of the so-called regulated professions, namely lawyers, civil engineers, medical doctors, certified accountants, etc. In these instances, as is to be expected, regulatory frameworks will differ significantly among host countries while some of them might even not allow it. This follows from the fact that the regulation of all issues pertaining to immigration, including participation and integration, fall within the ambit of state sovereignty. Host countries are entitled to adopt, without

³⁵ See Federal Office for Migration and Refugees, *The Impact of Immigration on Germany's Society*, Nuremberg, October 2005, <http://www.bamf.de> examining, inter alia, immigrants as entrepreneurs and immigrants as consumers.

restrictions, those rules they regard fit.³⁶ Thus, individual states or groups of states acting in unison are within their rights to determine the categories of aliens to whom employment will be offered and/or to place them hierarchically. A good example are the labour laws in the countries of the Persian Gulf (the so-called GCC countries), especially in those where the number of migrant workers has exceeded the citizenry. These laws stipulate that jobs should go first to the respective country's nationals, then to the nationals of other GCC states, then to non-Gulf Arabs (namely North African countries) and, finally, to all other aliens.³⁷

The host countries' ability to regulate immigration and in particular the position of migrant workers is not unlimited. There are restrictions in place and three of them will be examined here. The first restriction is based on the realization that migrants (at least those in lawful residence in host countries) enjoy the so-called 'acquired or vested rights'. This is a doctrine which was formulated some 90 years ago.³⁸ It is well known in EU law³⁹ and is currently debated in the context of the United Kingdom's eventual withdrawal from the EU.⁴⁰ If applied in the present

³⁶ Often the discussion on state sovereignty and immigration is derailed by insisting to discuss only the host countries' obligation to observe migrants' human rights, see e.g. L. Thompson, "Protection of Migrants' Rights and State Sovereignty", *UN Chronicle*, Vol. L No. 3, September 2013, <http://unchronicle.un.org/article/protection-migrants-rights-and-state-sovereignty/> But this is a matter having to do more with whether host countries' observe the international obligations assumed and not whether states have the unfettered right to pursue the immigration policies and regulations they prefer, provided that the peremptory rules of international law are observed.

³⁷ See A. Kapiszewski, *Arab Versus Asian Migrant Workers in the GCC Countries*, United Nations Expert Group Meeting on International Migration and Development in the Arab Region, UN Doc. UN/POP/EGM/2006/02, 22 May 2006, p. 8, http://www.un.org/en/development/desa/population/events/pdf/expert/11/P02_Kapiszewski.pdf

³⁸ Generally, see P. Lalive 'The doctrine of acquired rights' in International and Comparative Law Center (ed), *Rights and Duties of Private Investors Abroad*, M. Bender, New York, 1965, 145-200.

³⁹ See the so-called Acquired Rights Directive: Council Directive 2001/23/EC of 12 March 2001 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to the safeguarding of employees' rights in the event of transfers of undertakings, businesses or parts of undertakings or businesses, O.J. 22.3.2001 L82/16.

⁴⁰ Namely, whether citizenship rights acquired by British subjects in other EU Member States and vice versa could or should be protected after the withdrawal; see House of Lords, European Union

circumstances, it means that host countries are under a strict duty to observe, to shield and to abstain from deliberately acting against rights specifically enjoyed by migrants. The foundation of these rights is the host countries' duty to protect their fundamental rights, as this duty emanates from the corpus of relevant global and regional treaties and other multilateral instruments. As the latter have been accepted by the majority of states, as a growing number of national Constitutions make references to them, as domestic courts as well as the judicial organs of international organisations are increasingly citing their provisions, and as human rights are often a matter of discussion in inter-state dealings, it could safely be argued that they constitute norms of general application and states should always follow them. In short, they are internationally recognized rights. The application of migrant workers' acquired rights results in a number of restrictions. The principal one is that host countries are prevented from promulgating rules and regulations which violate their dignity and personality or breach other basic human rights, effectively downgrading them to second rate human beings. Thus host countries are not allowed, for example, to permit or tolerate the forced labour of migrants or their employment in analogous conditions. Moreover, they are obliged to investigate diligently all cases where migrants allege inhuman or degrading treatment, including exploitation by employers, and to prosecute and punish perpetrators.⁴¹

The second restriction concerns specific groups of states and flow from the rules and norms which are adopted by this group and take precedence over domestic legislation. The case at point is the EU legislation (not only the norms regulating immigration⁴² but EU law as a whole), which ranks higher in case of conflict with the rules adopted by Member States. This hierarchy of norms could be beneficial to

Committee, *The process of withdrawing from the European Union*, HL Paper 138, 4 May 2016, p. 9 <http://www.publications.parliament.uk/pa/ld201516/ldselect/ldcom/138/138.pdf>

41 Cf. Santiago Plan of Action adopted by the Second Summit of the Americas in April 1998, which specifically commits governments to, inter alia, protect migrant workers and their families from becoming victims of exploitation and abuse, <http://www.state.gov/p/wha/rls/59669.htm>

42 For an overview of current EU immigration law, see http://ec.europa.eu/immigration/who-does-what/more-information/explaining-the-rules-why-are-there-eu-rules-and-national-rules_en

migrant migrants in a number of cases.⁴³ For example, they should be able to rely directly on EU law if they believe that the host country's domestic legislation affecting them is not in compliance with it or if, for whatever reason, the host country has not incorporated domestically the EU rules on immigration. However, it should be noted that migrant workers are not protected directly. On the contrary, the safeguard is afforded because EU law is designed to be implemented and enforced in a non-discriminatory fashion. Thus, irrespective of who the recipient of the protection might be -it could be it the nationals of a Member State but it could also be the third country nationals residing therein- it leads to creating rights for the migrants, which at the same time are actionable and give rise to corresponding obligations for host countries.

Finally, the third restriction in the host country's unfettered ability to regulate the position and status of migrants has to do with the principle of reciprocity. Although reciprocity as a tool of international relations is not as widely employed as before,⁴⁴ it is still used in parts of the world (e.g. in the GCC countries) and is often found in bilateral agreements on migration. The latter are favoured by states because they offer targeted and detailed regulation of the mutual status of their citizens as migrants in the territory of the other state. In the present context, reciprocity means that a host country is obliged to treat the nationals coming from the other contracting party/ies in a pre-determined and specific manner because the latter has/have undertaken a similar obligation as regards the nationals coming from the former, which now becomes the country of origin.⁴⁵

⁴³ Cf. European Parliament, Directorate General for Internal Policies, *Discrimination of migrant workers at the workplace*, IP/A/EMPL/NT/2013-09, PE 518.768, May 2014, [http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/note/join/2014/518768/IPOL-EMPL_NT\(2014\)518768_EN.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/note/join/2014/518768/IPOL-EMPL_NT(2014)518768_EN.pdf)

⁴⁴ Generally, see R.O. Keohane, 'Reciprocity in International Relations' (1986) 40 *International Organization* 1-27.

⁴⁵ Bilateral agreements dealing with migration may also be concluded between an international organisation and a third state, see e.g. Art. 68 of the Euro-Mediterranean Agreement Establishing an Association between the European Community and its Member States of the one part and Egypt of the other part (2001), O.J. 30.11.2007 L 312/33. See also J.-P. Cassarino (ed.), *Unbalanced Reciprocities: Cooperation on Readmission in the Euro-Mediterranean Area*, Washington D.C.: Middle East Institute, Special Edition Viewpoints, 2010.

Notwithstanding these restrictions, the reality is that the question of migrant workers' participation in the economic life and their eventual integration in the host countries invariably is a reflection of how well planned and how adequately financed domestic policies are. Since these policies are adopted (or not adopted) primarily depending on the real or perceived needs and strengths of the host countries' economies and societies, it follows that different countries will tackle this issue of economic participation in a different manner. For example, host country A could take the view that to allow migrants to become entrepreneurs will have positive consequences for its economy and could also lead to their less problematic social integration. On the contrary, host country B could regard immigration as a quick and effective way to boost its ailing economy, which is in urgent need of large numbers of unskilled labour, and, consequently, it is not concerned with their socio-economic integration. The approach taken by host country A could indicate that it has accepted the fact that migrants are to remain in its territory for long (or longer) periods of time, while host country B presumably views immigration as a temporary situation and expects that they will return to the countries of origin when its economy has picked up.

In these two examples, it would be wrong to regard the country A as being the better or the more humane state towards immigrants and country B as being the exact opposite. Given that the formation and implementation of immigration policies fall within the scope of state sovereignty, in principle, any approach should be fundamentally accepted. As explained, integration processes involve on the one hand the immigrants, who most probably will not be a single group of people but will comprise many different sub-groups possibly separated along ethnic, language, religion, etc. lines, and on the other hand the host countries and their citizens. As in any multi-party process which takes place within a society and has diverse dynamics, it is not possible to keep all parties involved content at all times and to ensure a perfect equilibrium where there will be no winners and losers. Moreover, the integration of migrant workers is a multi-stage process requiring their own active participation. If, for whatever reason, they do not wish to be integrated in all or most aspects of the host countries' life, arguably they may not be forced to do so. For otherwise integration would equate to assimilation, namely a process where a host country deliberately implements policies geared towards the compulsory integration of its immigrant population. This should be considered unacceptable because it runs

against their acquired rights and violates their personality and ability to make their own choices without interference by anyone.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Migration is a complex process having different consequences for the countries involved. (e.g. demographic growth, human resources and jobs creation, etc.).⁴⁶ However, these consequences should not overshadow the fact that migrants deserve security and full enjoyment of their human rights and fundamental freedoms in host countries. This is a matter intricately related to their integration therein. As argued, for reasons of state sovereignty integration relates much more to the socio-economic sphere and much less to the political domain (although there are exemptions as regards host countries which are EU Member States). If implemented in a coherent and consistent manner, if due consideration is taken of the rights and aspirations of both the indigenous population and migrant workers, if the domestic legislation is observed and if the necessary funding is disbursed, all stakeholders stand to benefit. Unlike previous eras and with the exception of bilateral short-term immigration, nowadays migrant workers are resolved to spend their whole working life and, if possible, their retirement in the country/ies of destination. This reality puts the question of integration both as a goal but also as a method at the very heart of national immigration policies. Arguably, a large number of host countries (including states in Europe) have not yet come to terms with this reality. However, at least as far as the EU Member States as concerned, inward migration flows will have to increase for many decades if the current EU population is to rise slightly by 2050.⁴⁷ The successful handling of these flows will greatly depend on implementing sound integration policies. -

⁴⁶ According to European Commission, without net migration the working-age population will shrink by 12 per cent in 2030 and by 33 per cent in 2060 compared to 2009 levels, see Communication from the Commission, *An Agenda for new skills and jobs: A European contribution towards full employment*, COM (2010)682 final/2 of 26 November 2010.

⁴⁷ See European Commission, *The 2015 Ageing Report: Economic and budgetary projections for the 28 EU Member States (2013-2060)*, Brussels, 3 May 2015, http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/publications/european_economy/2015/ee3_en.htm